

Electrochemical studies on patent blue VF : a triphenylmethane dye

Rajeev Jain*, Meenakshi Bhargava and Nidhi Sharma

Department of Environmental Chemistry, Jiwaji University, Gwalior-474 011, India

E-mail : gwlsoSmica@sancharnet.in Fax : 91-751-2346209

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Electrochemical study of patent blue VF (4[4(*N*-diethylphenyl)-4",6"-disulfenylphenyl]-methylene-2,5-cyclohexadiene-1-(*N*-diethylimine), triphenylmethane dye, shows a single cathodic peak at 0.626 V for the dye solution (2×10^{-4} M), indicating a negative shift with increasing scan rate indicating the irreversible nature of the electrode process. After cpe negligible current (i_p , c) was observed and peak nearly gets diminished alongwith disappearance of colour. TLC and coulometric studies support the proposed reduction mechanism.

Synthetic dyes are difficult to degrade because of their complex structure and Xenobiotic properties. Moreover, certain dye precursors have been shown to be carcinogenic and mutagenic. Thus appropriate treatment of dye wastewater to remove colour and dye compounds is important. The degradation of synthetic dyes specially azo reactive dyes has been studied by other workers using different electrochemical techniques such as electrochemical bleaching of dye in an electrolyte solution containing halide ion as the activated ion¹⁻⁴, decolourization of azo dye in an anaerobic baffled reactor⁵ and decolourization of azo dye tartrazine by controlled potential electrolysis⁶. But the electrochemical studies performed on the triphenylmethane dyes discuss mostly the analytical applications. Polarographic reduction ranges of triphenylmethane dyestuffs were also the subject of various investigations^{7,8}. However, no systematic and comprehensive study could be found in literature on the electrochemical behavior and decolourization capability of Patent Blue VF.

In this study we have investigated the use of different solid electrodes (platinum and steel foil) in aqueous medium (with KCl as the supporting electrolyte) to gain insight into redox behavior of Patent Blue VF dye. In our study, the role of KCl is to suppress the migration current, and the halide ion does not participate at all in the electrode reaction. Patent Blue VF (4[4(*N*-diethylphenyl)-4",6"-disulfenyl phenyl]-methylene-2,5-cyclohexadiene-1-(*N*-diethyl-imine), is commonly used in textile industry and is known commercially as Acid Blue 1.

It was selected as a model compound representative of the dyes released from the effluents of textile industry. Cyclic voltammetric studies on Patent Blue VF were carried out at different pH and at different concentrations and scan rates. Based on voltammetric data and UV-visible spectropho-

metric studies, kinetic studies and rate determination of reaction rate have been carried out.

Results and discussion

Cyclic voltammetry :

The voltammogram of Patent Blue VF in aqueous neutral medium exhibits single cathodic and anodic peak. Cathodic peak potential shows a negative shift while anodic peak potential shows positive shift with increasing scan rate at both platinum and steel foil working electrodes (Fig. 1, Table 1). This negative shift in $E_{p,c}$ with increasing ν (scan rate) indicates irreversible electrode process.

A linear increase in peak current with increasing concentration is observed (Table 2). This tendency indicates that the electrode process is mainly diffusion-controlled with some adsorption contributions. The linear increase in peak current with increasing concentration indicates the difficulty in electro-reduction at higher concentration. At both platinum and steel electrodes linear plots were observed for peak current $i_{p,c}$ vs $\nu^{1/2}$. This behavior indicated the diffusion-controlled nature of the electrode process. As there was little deviation from the origin, it indicates that electrode reaction was mainly diffusion-controlled with some adsorption contributions⁹⁻¹⁴.

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of Patent Blue VF ($2 \times 10^{-4} M$ in distilled water) at Pt. working electrode at different scan rates : (I) 50, (II) 100, (III) 250, (IV) 500 mV/s.

Table 1. Electrochemical characteristics of Patent Blue VF in aqueous medium at different scan rates at steel foil working electrode

Conc. = $2 \times 10^{-4} M$					
Scan rate	$\nu^{1/2}$	$i_{p,c}$	$E_{p,c}$	$i_{p,a}$	$E_{p,a}$
m V/s		μA	V	μA	V
50	7.07				
(1)A		-441.50	-0.730	48.92	-0.068
(2)B		-1.26	-0.584	55.10	-0.815
100	10.00				
(1)A		-278.90	-0.907	-	-
(2)B		-3.61	-0.694	58.44	-0.801
250	15.81				
(1)A		-455.90	-1.096	-	-
(2)B		-4.75	-0.651	62.42	-0.762
500	22.36				
(1)A		-306.90	-0.751	-	-
(2)B		-17.68	-0.740	66.90	-0.719
1000	31.62				
(1)A		-391.40	-0.776	-	-
(2)B		-26.79	-0.740	75.68	-0.687

A = Before electrochemical treatment, B = after electrochemical treatment.

Table 2. Voltammetric characteristics of Patent Blue VF in distilled water at different concentrations at Pt. electrode

$\nu = 250 \text{ mV/s}$				
Conc. $\times 10^{-4} M$	$i_{p,c}$	$E_{p,c}$	$i_{p,a}$	$E_{p,c}$
	μA	V	μA	V
2.0	-10.72	-0.351	13.68	-0.217
4.0	-37.54	-0.479	30.78	-0.390
8.0	-90.72	-0.491	68.84	-0.366
12.0	-146.70	-0.485	97.96	-0.363
20.0	-279.30	-0.879	162.30	-0.096

exhibited well-defined reduction and corresponding oxidation peaks in the pH range 2.5–10.5. In highly acidic pH (2.5, 3.8) two peaks were observed but as the pH of the medium is increased peaks merge into one. In the entire pH range single oxidation peak is observed. Both cathodic and anodic peak potential show negative shift with increasing pH. The data pertaining to voltammetric characteristics of Patent Blue VF at various pH at platinum foil electrode are depicted in Table 3.

Controlled potential electrolysis :

Controlled potential electrolysis of Patent Blue VF dye in aqueous medium (conc. $2 \times 10^{-4} M$) was carried out at an electrolysis potential of -1.20 V using platinum foil and steel foil working electrodes. After $\sim 8 \text{ h}$ of electrolysis the dye solution was completely decolourised with a significant

Electrochemical behavior at varying pH :

Cyclic voltammograms of Patent Blue VF ($2 \times 10^{-4} M$)

Table 3. Voltammetric characteristics of Patent Blue VF at different pH

Conc. = $2 \times 10^{-4} M$, $\nu = 100 \text{ mV/s}$

pH	$i_{p,c}$ μA		$E_{p,c}$ V		$i_{p,a}$ μA	$E_{p,a}$ V
	(i)	(ii)	(i)	(ii)		
2.5						
(1)A	-296.20	-219.90	-0.762	-0.573	94.22	-0.349
(2)B	-44.04	-	-0.950	-	16.59	-0.971
3.8						
(1)A	-193.70	-139.20	-0.826	-0.669	90.94	-0.452
(2)B	-78.21	-	-0.911	-	56.79	-0.694
5.6						
(1)A	-101.90	-	-0.765	-	83.99	-0.587
(2)B	-67.52	-	-0.900	-	53.98	-0.683
6.5						
(1)A	-77.28	-	-0.722	-	75.70	-0.605
(2)B	-62.64	-	-0.833	-	49.35	-0.826
8.8						
(1)A	-72.31	-	-0.833	-	64.32	-0.722
(2)B	-52.79	-	-0.854	-	64.32	-0.722
10.5						
(1)A	-84.70	-	-0.854	-	50.50	-0.758
(2)B	-72.50	-	-0.886	-	105.40	-0.676

A = Before electrochemical treatment, B = after electrochemical treatment.

decrease in cathodic peak current (Fig. 2). Peak current when plotted as a function of time exhibited gradual decrease initially and later becoming parallel to the base line. The number of electrons 'n' involved in the reduction of Patent Blue VF was found to be one at platinum working electrode.

Spectral studies :

UV-visible spectra of Patent Blue VF solution ($2 \times 10^{-4} M$ in aqueous neutral medium) gave λ_{max} at 635 nm. When the electrolysis potential of -1.20 V was applied the absorbance at 635 nm decreases gradually with the progress of electrolysis. Decrease in cathodic peak current and absorbance were monitored at regular intervals at this wavelength. After $\sim 8 \text{ h}$ of electrolysis the peak current decreases significantly and a colourless solution is obtained. The rate of decrease in current and absorbance with time were found to be obeying first order rate expression. The values of first order rate constants for decrease in current and absorbance at platinum foil working electrode for Patent Blue VF are presented in Table 4.

Chromatographic studies :

Electro-reduction products were separated after carrying out controlled product electrolysis (cpe). After cpe the electrolysed solution was subjected to thin layer chromatography using dioxan : water and acetone : water as the mobile phase. A single spot was observed in dioxan : water

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms of Patent Blue VF ($2 \times 10^{-4} M$) at Pt. working electrode, $\nu = 250 \text{ mV/s}$ at different pH : (I) 2.5, (II) 3.8, (III) 5.6, (IV) 6.5, (V) 10.5.

Table 4. First order rate constants for decrease in current and absorbance for Patent Blue VF at Pt. working electrode

Parameter measured	Rate constant K (min^{-1})	Half-life of reaction ($t^{1/2}$)	Observed rate of reaction ($R_{\text{abs}}/\text{min}^{-1}$)
Decrease in current with time	4.61×10^{-3}	150 min^{-1}	9.21×10^{-7}
Decrease in absorbance with time	3.45×10^{-2}	20.1 min^{-1}	6.91×10^{-6}

mobile phase while with acetone : water a broad band merging with mobile phase was observed.

Chemical oxygen demand :

After controlled potential electrolysis, Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) was calculated for both initial coloured and final electrolysed solution as per standard methods¹⁵. The COD of the electrolysed solution shows a significant decrease from 1520 mg/L of the initial coloured compound to 560 mg/L in the final electrolysed solution indicating a significant decrease in the toxicity level of the electrolysed product formed.

Redox mechanism :

On the basis of cyclic voltammetry, coulometric mea-

surements, spectral studies and chromatographic studies following mechanism may be proposed for the reduction of Patent Blue VF. In a single electron reduction step, one electron is accepted by nitrogen of species A to give B.

Experimental

Controlled potential electrolysis was carried on BAS CV-27 cyclic voltammograph in connection with a Digital Electronic 2000 Omnigraph X-Y/t recorder. A three-electrode cell was used for carrying out electrolysis. The working electrodes are platinum ($3 \times 3 \text{ cm}^2$) and steel foil ($4.5 \times 3.5 \text{ cm}^2$), the reference is Ag/AgCl and auxiliary electrode a platinum wire. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded using EG & G Princeton Applied Research VersaStat-II Potentiostat. The pH-metric measurements were made on Hach EC-40 Bench top pH/ISE meter. For identification of end products thin layer chromatography (TLC) was employed. Ready made silica gel plates (60₂₅₄) of E. Merck company were used. The spectral studies were carried out using UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Elico SL-159).

Reagents and solution : Patent Blue VF of Standard Fluka Chemika was used. $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ stock solution of Patent Blue VF in 50 ml of distilled water was prepared. 1.0 M KCl in distilled water was used as a supporting electrolyte. B.R. buffers in the pH range 2.5-12.0 were used. All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

Procedure : For cyclic voltammetry (CV) and controlled potential electrolysis (cpe) the solution was prepared by taking 9.0 ml of the stock solution and 1.0 mL of 1.0 M KCl. The solution was deaerated by passing nitrogen gas for about 15 minutes and the cyclic voltammograms were recorded in the beginning of the experiment and then the solution was subjected to cpe at -1.20 V . Further at the end of electrolysis, the voltammograms were also recorded. For TLC studies both coloured and electrolysed solutions were loaded on the plate and then developed in the selected mobile phase.

For coulometric determination of number of electrons 'n' consumed in the reduction, cyclic voltammograms were recorded at a potential slightly higher than peak potential. With the progress of the electrolysis the colour of the solution gradually faded away and the current also decreases exponentially with time and become practically zero after some time. Value of Q was read directly and by the application of $Q = nFN$, the value of 'n' could be calculated.

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